

Appendices B and C for “Revisiting the
massive star-forming complex RCW 122: New
millimeter and submillimeter study”

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B Spectra of detected transitions

Figure B.1: Observed spectra of detected transitions in clump A in T_{mb} . The transitions are indicated in the top left corner of each panel. The red curves show the Gaussian fits to the lines.

Figure B.2: Observed spectra of detected transitions in clump B in T_{mb} . The transitions are indicated in the top left corner of each panel. The red curves show the Gaussian fits to the lines.

Figure B.3: Observed spectra of detected transitions in clump C in T_{mb} . The transitions are indicated in the top left corner of each panel. The red curves show the Gaussian fits to the lines.

Figure B.4: Observed spectra of detected transitions in clump D in T_{mb} . The transitions are indicated in the top left corner of each panel. The red curves show the Gaussian fits to the lines.

Figure B.5: Observed spectra of detected transitions in clump E in T_{mb} . The transitions are indicated in the top left corner of each panel. The red curves show the Gaussian fits to the lines.

C Zeroth-order moment maps of detected transitions

Figure C.1: Zeroth-order moment maps of molecular lines detected for clump A (color tonalities, in K km s^{-1}), superimposed onto the $870 \mu\text{m}$ emission (black contours, as presented in Fig. 1)

Figure C.2: Zeroth-order moment maps of molecular lines detected for clump B (color tonalities, in K km s^{-1}), superimposed onto the $870 \mu\text{m}$ emission (black contours, as presented in Fig. 1)

Figure C.3: Zeroth-order moment maps of molecular lines detected for clump C (color tonalities, in K km s^{-1}), superimposed onto the $870 \mu\text{m}$ emission (black contours, as presented in Fig. 1)

Figure C.4: Zeroth-order moment maps of molecular lines detected for clump D (color tonalities, in K km s^{-1}), superimposed onto the $870 \mu\text{m}$ emission (black contours, as presented in Fig. 1)

Figure C.5: Zeroth-order moment maps of molecular lines detected for clump E (color tonalities, in K km s^{-1}), superimposed onto the $870 \mu\text{m}$ emission (black contours, as presented in Fig. 1)